

Comparative Study of Blood Pressure and Pulse Rate Between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was “comparative study of blood pressure and pulse rate between high achieving and low achieving national level footballers”. The subjects for this study were male national football players. One hundred forty four subjects were selected for the study. Seventy two were those high achieving national level footballers and seventy two were those low achieving national level footballers. The age group of footballers was ranged between 19 to 28 years. To determine the comparative differentials of blood pressure and pulse rate between high achieving and low achieving national level footballers, the test of significance (*t*-ratio) was employed. Further, the level of significance was set at 0.05 level of confidence. The findings of the study reveal that there was significant difference was found in case of systolic blood pressure and pulse rate between high achieving national level footballers exhibited better systolic blood pressure and pulse rate in comparison with the low achieving national level footballers. the study also shows that there was no significant difference in diastolic blood pressure between high achieving and low achieving national level footballers may be due to the reason that the players were almost of the same standard with a similar kind of experience which must have been a probable cause.

Keyword:

Blood Pressure and Pulse Rate

1. INTRODUCTION

From its very simple form, sports has emerged into highly organized activity of human society. Sports is highly organized form of play and play is a general innate tendency. Play is very important for preservation, growth and development of organism. Sports is as old as the human society and it holds a prominent place in the modern life. Millions of people participate in sports activities, watch and read about them and spend billions of dollars annually on sports activities and equipment. It now enjoys a popularity which outstrips any other form of social activity. It has become an integral part of the educational process as physical education and sports have been included in the regular curriculum. The students are taught various games and sports in a systematic manner. Besides teaching, the students are evaluated in their performance. Many people participate in games and sports for deriving physical, mental, social and emotional benefits. Competitive element is inherent in sports, as now sportsmen participate to win and achieve laurels for them as well as for their country contrary to earlier philosophy of participation in sports competition for sake of participation, In other words, competitive sports has come to be valued in society. Towards the attainment of top performance, the physical educationists and coaches are trying to bring the new innovations as they are deeply involved in the preparation of sportsmen for present and future. The modern trend

in preparation of sportsmen is to proceed in a scientific manner and take its help of allied sciences to achieve a top level performance.

2. OBJECTIVES

1. To compare the blood pressure of High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.
2. To compare the pulse rate of High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

Hypothesis It was also hypothesized that there may be significant difference in Blood Pressure and Pulse Rate between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

Methodology The study was confined to One hundred forty four Senior Level Footballers .Seventy two High Achieving and Seventy two Low Achieving National Level Footballers were selected (age group of 19 to 28 years). The data was collected in the 68th Shantosh Trophy National Football Tournament held Kanchanjangha Stadium Siliguri from 24th February to 9th March 2014. One hundred forty four subjects by administering the tests for the selected test items on the different National level football players.

Sampling The subjects for this study were male National Football players, One hundred forty four subjects were selected for the study. Seventy two were those High Achieving National Level Footballers and Seventy two were those Low Achieving National Level Footballers. The age group of footballers was ranged between 19 to 28 years.

3. PROCEDURES

Blood pressure was measured by Sphygmomanometer and stethoscopes. Pulse Rate was measured by stopwatch.

4. STATISTICAL PROCEDURE

To determine the comparative differentials of Blood pressure and pulse rate between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers, the test of significance ('t'-Ratio) was employed. Further, the level of significance was set at 0.05 level of confidence.

5. RESULTS

Table 1: Significance of Difference Between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers on Pulse Rate in Numbers of Beats

Variables	M-1	M-2	MD	SE	't' Ratio	Required 't' Ratio
Pulse Rate	67.53	69.40	01.87	00.53	03.53*	01.98

* Significant at 0.05 level of Confidence

M_1 = Mean of High Achieving National Level Footballers

M_2 = Mean of Low Achieving National Level Footballers

From the above Table 1, it is revealed that there was significant difference in case of Pulse Rate Test as calculated 't' value (03.53) was more than tabulated 't' value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance with 142 degree of freedom. Thus, it may be concluded that there was significant difference between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers related to Pulse Rate Test, in which mean Pulse Rate Test is significantly lower for High Achieving National Level Footballers than Low Achieving National Level Footballers at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the Table 1 are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Graphical Depiction of Mean values of Pulse Rate Test between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers

Table 2: Significance of Difference Between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers on Systolic Blood Pressure in Numbers of Beats

Variables	M-1	M-2	MD	SE	't' Ratio	Required 't' Ratio
Systolic Blood Pressure	124.62	140.24	15.62	3.97	3.93*	1.98

* Significant at 0.05 level of Confidence

M_1 = Mean of High Achieving National Level Footballers

M_2 = Mean of Low Achieving National Level Footballers

From the above Table 2, it is revealed that there was significant difference in case of Systolic Blood Pressure Test as calculated 't' value (3.93) was more than tabulated 't' value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance with 142 degree of freedom. Thus, it may be concluded that there was significant difference between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers related to Systolic Blood Pressure Test, in which mean Systolic Blood Pressure Test is significantly lower for High Achieving National Level Footballers than Low Achieving National Level Footballers at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the Table 2 are presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 : Graphical Depiction of Mean values of Systolic Blood Pressure Test between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers

Table 3: Significance of Difference Between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers on Diastolic Blood Pressure in MM. GH.

Variables	M-1	M-2	MD	SE	't' Ratio	Required 't' Ratio
Diastolic Blood Pressure	81.67	82.14	00.47	01.12	00.42	01.98

* Significant at 0.05 level of Confidence

M_1 = Mean of High Achieving National Level Footballers

M_2 = Mean of Low Achieving National Level Footballers

From the above Table 3, it is revealed that there was insignificant difference in case of Diastolic Blood Pressure Test as calculated 't' value (00.42) was less than tabulated 't' value (1.98) at 0.05 level of significance with 142 degree of freedom. Thus, it may be concluded that there was insignificant difference between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers related to Diastolic Blood Pressure Test, in which mean Diastolic Blood Pressure Test is insignificantly lower for High Achieving National Level Footballers than Low Achieving National Level Footballers at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the Table 3 are presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Graphical Depiction of Mean Values of Diastolic Blood Pressure Test between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers

6. DISCUSSION

The findings of the study reveal that there was a significant difference in Pulse Rate between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers. It may be due to the reason that in Pulse Rate where the subjects who were in the High Achieving National Level Footballers had pulmonary circulation blood leaves the right ventricle via pulmonary artery. The pulmonary artery is divided into two branches for left and right lungs. Within the lungs arteries are divided from arterioles to which further divide into capillaries. As the subjects had undergone systematic training programme the ability of the wall of capillaries might have increased the oxygen absorption ability during inhalation. As the capillaries unite to form venues and veins where by the blood leaves the lungs via pulmonary veins emptying the left atrium of the heart. This would have influenced the heart to function even after circulating required amount of blood to the working muscles and as the subjects were hyper tensed due to the effect of pollution the systematic pranayama practices might have improved the working condition of heart reducing the pulse rate.

The findings of the study reveal that there was a significant difference in Systolic Blood Pressure between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers. It may be due to the fact that in systolic blood pressure where the subjects who were in the High Achieving National Level Footballers had undergone practices of different training have improved and influenced higher function of central nervous system thereby improving the working ability of sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system. Another reason of decrease in systolic blood pressure may be due to the improvement in the elasticity of blood vessels which otherwise might have contracted.

The study also shows that there was no significant difference in Diastolic Blood Pressure between the study shows that there was no significant difference in Diastolic Blood Pressure between High Achieving and Low Achieving National Level Footballers. It may be due to the fact that two categories Footballers like High Achieving and Low

Achieving National Level Footballers were undergoing almost similar type of training programme. It may also be the reason that both groups were almost equal in experience and competition.

Further, it is also a known fact that motor skills and large muscle psychometric ability are far more specific. In addition, it is a known fact that it may be a matter of chance that an individual who is highly coordinated in one type of performance will be excellent or clumsy in co-ordination in other sports. Successful patterns of specific traits are generally not the same for all sportsmen. Usually the sportsmen have some common characteristics and the pattern of these characteristics varies from sportsman to sportsman and a successful sportsman may be low on a particular trait but may compensate for strength in another. It has been observed that there are few extraordinary individuals in the field of physical education whose ability to acquire skills in different games and sports is comparatively faster than others and hence they score better in practical than others. Probably, the reason behind their quick pick-up of skills may lie in the abundance of different variables and their combination of Physiological Abilities.

7. CONCLUSION

- There was significant difference was found in case of Pulse Rate where High Achieving National Level Footballers exhibited better Pulse Rate in comparison with the Low Achieving National Level Footballers.
- There was significant difference was found in case of Systolic Blood Pressure where High Achieving National Level Footballers exhibited better Systolic Blood Pressure in comparison with the Low Achieving National Level Footballers.
- There was insignificant difference was found in case of Diastolic Blood Pressure where High Achieving National Level Footballers exhibited better Systolic Blood Pressure in comparison with the Low Achieving National Level Footballers.

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